

Narrative Analysis of Ethiopian Medical students Major Department Choice: Experience Factors, Performance and Challenge

Abstract

This study investigated the factors, challenges, and experience on school performance that influence major choice among three fourth year medicine students of Hawassa University. Highest score in UEE has required from students to pursue and join as their choice of interest in medical school. The study uses qualitative research method and the interview information has narrated in recurrent themes. It is important to understand the reasons behind this decision if we are to choose the best applicants for medical schools and enable them to pursue satisfying careers, and also address the consequences beforehand. Hence, three students were selected purposively and interview was conducted. It found that, the social status of being a doctor, job security, employment opportunity, good salary, helping people and characters in a fiction were factors to select medicine. On the other hand, with regard to factors relating to personal background, early childhood experiences, and parental motives influenced the career choices of students. The narration sought that, early decision to join medicine was contributing to performing high in prior schools. However we cannot generalize the finding as it was done insignificant number respondents in one college. Nevertheless, this study was able to provide valuable information on the reasons for choosing a professional career among Hawassa University fourth year Medicine students. This study suggested researchers interested in the area to conduct studies that will helpful to fill the gaps on the current study findings and to build up the issue in the context of Ethiopia.

Key words: *Choice, decisions, medicine, factors, narration, UEE*

1. Introduction

The history of Ethiopian higher education showed that, students selection for entry to higher learning institutions and particular placement to fields of studies mostly have held by centrally

established institution that has mandated by Ministry of Education and Universities have little room of engagement in the process (UNESCO, 1988).

The act of choosing college major is one of the most profound decisions in student's life and it has in need of considering and analyzing complex information (**Amir and Gait, 2013**). Asking early school children's a question that related with jobs want to be when grown up; they mostly respond to become princess, King, Doctor, Lawyer and others prestige careers (Schaefer, Rivera& Ophals, 2010). However, in many studies of pupils response on job aspirations in early ages found that, there have very limited relationship between knowledge of college major choice and future career goals (Johnson, 2000).

Students' choices of major field of study in colleges or universities have emerged as early as lower high schools (Schafer, et.al, 2010). Current researches strengthened Schafer and his colleagues finding, at all grade levels learners have aspiration of future choices of study but it emerge in the middle grades. This research aimed to study students currently pursuing medicine field at Hawasa University in their college major choices related constructs and activities engaged in prior schools by using qualitative research method. .

Early examples of researches into interest of students to select college major and factor for their decision were studied (Semela, 2010; National Middle School Association (NMSA), 2010; Duffy and Sedlacek, 2007 and *Hirschi and Lage, 2005*).Duffy and Sedlacek (2007), identify students decision of college major choice appropriateness have been judged by knowing contextual values that emanated from deciders lived experience. Specifically, the major factor for field of study decisions on college has relied highly on the work values that have categorized within four basic dimensions: intrinsic, extrinsic, social, and prestige. The term values refer to scripted wishes of a student to choose a field of study restricted by norms and social expectations (ibid, 2007).

Findings affirmed that; most students career selection have influenced by lack of knowledge, orientation and related construct and it made their decisions among the more salient difficulties they face (Amir and Gati, 2010 and Schafer, et.al, 2010).Recognizing the factors of major choice

and the drawbacks of choice decision will help to support students on making choice of major to be aligned with their interest and ability. As a result, there have been considerable interventions that help students to make informed and knowledgeable decisions of college major field of study in western context namely, in Europe and USA. To this end, it suggested delivering career programs, counseling service, conducting assessment at a certain interval in their educational system and teachers mentoring (NMSA, 2010).

However, to date, little is known about career interventions and the underlying factors that affect interest to study college major among African students. The study focused on Ethiopia, particularly medicine that has gain prominent value in the public (Tsion, Damen, Wubegzier and Miliard, 2017; Assefa, Adane and Aneme, 2008). Tsion and her colleagues (2017) identified the reasons, health services were partly relied on the direct linkage of medical activity with life care of individuals in the society, at the same time high attention given by government, graduates from medical sciences can incur more payment as compared to other professions, and mostly considered by the public as profession for printing/making/ money.'

For most major field of studies, student's assignment in HEIs have decided based on the aggregate score achieved in UEE as compared to other students with similar interest of choice (Mulu, 2014; MOE, 2008; Getachew, 2008 and UNESCO, 1988). In his *PhD dissertation* Mulu(2012) apart from other fields of studies, medicine students have highest score as compared to other students who took the exam in the same year, and their interest should be maintained when the number of highest scoring students were not exceed the specified HEIs admission quota.

In Ethiopian HEIs, Choice highly depends on University Entrance Examination (UEE) aggregate score and believed to have drawbacks (Semela, 2010). Semela's study demonstrated that, the majority of students assigned to study physics without their choice were blamed for lack of interest to learn, low achievement, lack of academic success and low academic self-concept even as compared to their counterparts assigned in other natural science departments. Similarly, a report of UNESCO (1988) asserts that, in Ethiopian schools college major choices have held with little or no orientations to students on career guidance and counseling; i.e. means either in the

schooling years or at the time of their career choice to HEI students have not accesses to career programs; regarding the function of the sub tests are unknown (Addis Ababa University (AAU), 2008; Gerachew, 2008 and Gilbert, 1967); either assesses students' personality interests or ability (any other function) were unclear (UNESCO, 1988).

Despite this, the enrolment policy of HEIs has exacerbates the inequalities created by disregarding lower scoring students' choice of interest and further caused them to frustration and discouragement (e.g., Semela 2010 and Woodward, 1969). Students' who score high in UEE have greater probabilities of getting their top ranked choices of college major fields. On the other hand, enrollments to medical school highly probable and for those students who have the highest score from the high UEE scores. Researches such as that conducted by Mulu (2012) have found out that, 97 per cent of students who enroll to pursue medical education have joined with their first choice of interest. Further, for medicine majoring students the policy have respecting their interest and the demand in the health service further re-reinforce them by guaranteeing future employment (TSION, et.al, 2017) as compared to other students who joined in other fields with high scores.

Having discussed how enrollment in HEIs and major field of study of Ethiopian students' were dependent on UEE result , this paper conducts a qualitative research on field of study related constructs particularly on medical students using narrative analysis methodology. For the attainment of the study objectives, participants interviewed data were recorded and carefully transcribed to emerge recurrent themes (read Flick, 2014), The themes fall under there broad categories: the first, underlying reasons of choice or factors such as societal values, models, prestigious, character in a book and others; the second decisions to study medicine in HEI and its contribution prior school performance and the third challenges of medical school students in the HEIs. The research employed deep interview with recommended interview techniques and it try to discover possible uncovered constructs related with pursuing medicine in HEI and aspiration with three available medical students of Hawassa University. In this paper, interview data were narrated for these three fourth year students (aged 22-26 years).

It is imperative to frame the research on the following research questions;

- How students lived experience, social values, models and other factors have shape their career orientation or decision to choose medicine?
- What are the contributions of deciding to study medicine to school performance and motivation to learn?
- what are the challenges medical students face for the success of their schooling?

2. Background

2.1. HE in Ethiopia: Historic Overview of Careers and Medical study

The ancient nation in Africa, Ethiopia like most countries of the world, the society had engaged in numerous jobs as part of their livelihood. For centuries, people have got either encouragement or discouragement on the jobs they did by the society whereas some improvements have demonstrated recently. The problems of inner cultural devaluation of people by their jobs have simply known by the lived experiences of Ethiopian dwellers of the past and present (for more read, Harold Marcus, 1994)

As explained earlier, the jobs like blacksmith; Goldsmith; Clay maker; Carpenter, Weaver, and leather making, gender and the like have gone beyond cultural devaluation and stereotype. So far, a lists of activities have been identified as being forbidden to the ordinary (termed in Amharic “Chiwa” or Respected) people with persons (“Fuga” or Casted) engaged in the aforementioned jobs (Versus the two); making marriage, church service, greeting, social contact and other cultural segregation.

Following Italian invasions, to alleviate the believed cause of the nation’s underdevelopment; the Emperor at that time launched a proclamation and announced any stereotypes of segregating people by their jobs were strictly forbidden and doing it had brought sanction of punishment (Ayalew, 2000). Past evidences showed that, the traditional administrative structure, the ancient Ethiopian orthodox Christian and other religions have contributed in shaping the cultural devaluation or disrespecting. However, the historic Christian church has profound and undeniable contributions to the country’s education, keeps written evidence and develops its own script that made Ethiopia as the only country in Sub-Saharan Africa (Teshome, 1979).

Later on, in 1908, western education was started during the regime of emperor Minilik II (Ayalew, 2000), and its aim was in need of citizens to cope up with western ideas and to modernize the country. This initiative was after the Italian invaders unexpectedly utilize flying rockets as military science and which is new and challenge, though defeated by Ethiopian armies, Emperor Minilik expressed his feeling saying:

“በማጪዎም ሲመች ይገቡ ነበር፤ (They entered in Machew)

በአጋዴም ሲመች ይገቡ ነበር፤(They entered in Ogaden)

በሰማይ ላይ ገቡ በማናውቀው ሀገር።” (They entered in the sky which is unknown)

He understood the gaps existed between Italian and Ethiopia with regard to modernity and technology. The gap ignited a candle on the mind of the king opted to start modern education and the structure of the educational system was a fusion derivative of Great Britain and African countries, for example Sudan and Kenya in three level system (4+4+4) (Adane,1996 and Kehoe, 1962). It looks as if paradoxical; modern education has faced greater resistance by the church leaders and caused people’s unwillingness to send their children to schools. The predecessor of emperor Minilik II, his daughter princeZewditu declared educational proclamation to the public in 1929 to assuage the problem and it included huge amount of money 50 birr as a punishment (Ayalew, 2000 and Adane, 1996). It stated as; “all those who do not send their sons and daughters to school to learn writing and reading skills which are necessary to identify the good and evils and develop fear of God and there will be punished 50 Birr.”

Later on, in the subsequences decades, the public resistance of western education has replaced by appreciation of the teaching profession and they demonstrate the new value by singing in the teacher’s wedding as follows:

“የእኛሙሽሪት ኩሪኩሪ

ወሰዳትአስተማሪ”

To dignify the teacher with historic rhymes; —marriage female feel happy and joy, “because your husband is a teacher” in that people sing to glorify the teachers found in any level of schooling.

From mid-1940's and throughout the 1950's students were expected to sit for the General School Leaving Certificate Examination and the practice began to decline after the mandate is given to the 1951 established University College at Addis Ababa (Adane, 1996). The ancient and historic country in Africa, Ethiopia has a large, mostly rural population with limited accesses to health services that resulted in high rate of health related problem occurrence like, TB, malaria, nutritional deficiencies, frequently occurrence of epidemics, maternal deaths, respiratory infections, neonatal mortality, diarrheal diseases and disabilities.

However, evidences in the past showed that, health workers are not only sufficient in number but also rarely available particularly in rural part of the country in which more than 85% of the population dwells (CSA 2014). To address the community health needs, the country established the first medical education program in 1960s (Kehoe, 1962) and its objective is to produce competent, compassionate and community oriented doctors for Ethiopia with internationally recognized standard (AAU, 2008).

In both, the historic past and the current practices have evidenced that, students entry to the Medical education has expected to score the highest aggregate score in the leaving examination (Mulu, 2012; MOE; 2008 and Gilbert, 1967). The highest scoring student's interest to study medicine have evidenced that , socially prestigious, offer opportunity to explore, attract good salaries, guaranteeing job, offer people opportunities to help others, to make good money and driven by service were the major reasons of choice (TSION, et.al, 2017 and Wakgar, 2012).

Besides, professional doctors and medicine students have highly valued and esteemed by both the societies and the government and devaluing the field was little or not at all throughout the discipline's history. For instance, the profound values that have been given for teaching profession in the past and latter followed by strong devaluation were not evidenced in the medical discipline (TSION, et.al, 2017).

Research findings evidenced that, in recent year's health workers are not sufficiently available particularly in rural part of the country in which more than 85% of the population dwells. The demand gap further widens by the population growth alarming rate followed by the brain drain of doctors from the country. To alleviate the problem, HEIs designed accelerated program for Advanced standing applicants with B.Sc. The policy might well reinforce the leaving examination highest scoring students by assigning to their interested fields, but the highest demand in the healthy service re-reinforce medical students by guaranteeing future employment as compared to other fields of interest.

It is imperative to conduct a study on medical students' major choice decision in the following reasons: most of the studies are conducted in other major department students and focus on self-efficacy and pays little attention career choice, studies on overall evaluations of HEIs but gave little attention to career related issues and (Semela, 2010) and little research have been conducted on the challenges of medical students.

3. Major frame of the study

Reviewing existing studies in western countries (e.g. Amir and Gati, 2013; Thompson and Dahling, 2010; Wille, De Fruyt and Feys, 2010; Duffly and Sedlacek, 2007; Hirschi and Läge, 2007; Porter and Umbach, 2006; Rosenbloom, Ash and LeAnne, 2006;) and African countries (Mulu, 2012; Edoh and Alutu, 2011; Semela, 2010; Agulanna and Nwachukwu, 2004) indicates that students college major choice is affected by various factors like parents, teachers, peer group, radio, television and books that they experienced in their day to day life. Despite the apparent similarities, however, the significance factor to place students based on their interest to HEI and major field of study has accounted most on the aggregate achievement score in UEE. For instance, a study (Mulu, 2012) in public HEIs found out that the placement of students to major department, the choice of field is respected in faculties ranging from 97% for medicine, 91% for law, 85% in technology and 64% business and economics have observed and they study in college with keen interest for the profession and looked to be pleased with their placement.

To the contrary, in a study of (e.g. Semela, 2010) showed that, the majority of the respondents from the College of Education and the Faculty of Sciences had joined their fields of study without their choices/by assignment; as a result students in the aforementioned faculties pursuing

their study in college were not for love of the profession rather for the sake of getting job and lack of other option to change.

Considerable gap, faculties with more applicants such as medicine and law are in a better position to enroll students with better UEE results and with faculties with fewer applicants such as education face problems of enrolling students with better scores. However, studies on UEE students result and major career choice factors showed that, there is no significance relationship UEE with academic self-concept and academic performance, instead UEE has showed significant relationship with attitude, value orientation, admission preferences and motivation (Getachew, 2008; UNESCO,1988 and Gilbert, 1967).

It is imperative to raise questions to medicine students to answer in the study; are the lived experience, social values, models and other factors shape their career orientation and decision to choose medicine, when the decision to study medicine incepted?, what are the challenges they face in medical school, are the challenges perceived as impeding factors to their performance and motivation to learn in HEI?

As part of this study, we conducted interviews with three fourth year medical students by two interviewers at the end of first semester. In each of the interviews, they were asked questions that have aimed to address the above aforementioned issues. At the beginning of the interview, they were asked regarding their background history (including whether they would be the first in their family to enter HEI, etc.), their experiences with health related activities and their aspiration towards future study; their attitude, interest and motivation to their experiences prior to attending in medical school and after pursuing in the medical field, their orientation, interest and reasons of choice of medicine.

This intended to address gaps of few research works conducted in medical students related with career related constructs, paying high emphasis to those fields of studies students placed with low UEE and interest gaps and most research are conducted in HE using quantitative approaches.

4. Method

In order to answer the research questions, the study employees qualitative research design, which according to Davis (2007), “Good qualitative helps to understand a complex phenomenon, you must consider the multiple ‘realities’ experienced by the participants themselves the “insider’ perspectives.”

The description of people’s lived experiences, events, or situations is often described as ‘thick’ (Denzin, 1989), meaning attention is given to rich detail, meaningful social and historical contexts and experiences, and the significance of emotional content in an attempt to open up the word of whoever or whatever is being studied. The study employees’ narrative analysis using the record interviews of three students (male=1 and female=2) and this type of research is distinguished by the *life story* method, in which people describe their life experiences via storytelling.

Strategies for data collection are open and depend on context. Revisions are made until the researcher is satisfied that the direction taken affords the greatest potential for discovery, meaningful answers to questions posed, or the generation of new hypotheses (or questions). Of course, qualitative researchers begin with an interest or guiding question, but early decisions about what type of data should be collected and how it should be collected will undoubtedly be revised as the research progresses.

5. Analysis and results

The sample students are given pseudo names for the confidentiality and privacy issues as follows:

5.1. Gemechu’s story

A 24 years old and a third child in the family; Gemechu, he was born in one of the zone capital town of Ethiopia. Gemechu’s father was died in his early age as he hears from his mother. His mother soon took, together with his sister to another town found near to the capital city of the country, at that time his mother was pregnant his younger sister. .

During the interview Gemechu Alene is fourth year and semester one medical student at Hawasa University. When asked about his lived school experience before joining medical school, Gemechu tells us:

My Mom gives due attention to Education, when I start school I am the youngest... My mother encouraged me.., she has a desire from us to learn properly []. Aha... I started to read. To make my mam to become Happy, I strongly devoted to acquire knowledge in education ... God supports me and I became clever student in early schools.

5.1.1. Other activities he involved in his early schooling, was asked:

Yah...Side by side of education, I read books. When I was a grade three student, I read my first book that my elder sister borrowed from the school; I remember “Konjowochu” was the title of the book. I hide myself from her and I read when I was a grade three student. Up to grade six, I read many books that my sister borrowed...

When we enter grade seven, in our school formally students are allowed to enter to the library, when they arrive at grade seven. At that time I started entering in the library and I precede reading fictions. I read most of the fictions when I am grade 7 and 8. My score of grade 8th regional exam is the first top score from the zone and second from the region.

5.1.2. When asked the mechanisms he accommodates reading books out of the school subject and to become clever....

My vision...aha... Making my mother to become proud of me...You see succeeding in school was my plan...Always to rewarded...You know, “Seni 30”, the day to receive a card. To be rewarded is my obligation and it was the only thing, I gave to my mother as a gift. In my mind, I believe on this. I become the top ranked student and rewarded.

When, I am retrieving my child hood. I sometimes asked my mother about my father. She told me things, he drink, had come home to disturb, picked knife, terrorized her to slaughter. She said me repeatedly; you didn't lose any time thinking about him. She made me to perceive my father as bad. In most of my school years, my concern about my father was eliminated.

My mother reared me...Her generosity, love and empathy. She fulfill basic things for me everything

5.2.Blien's Story

Blien Getaneh, who was born and grow in one of small town in Oromia region, is reported the first child in her family and, 22 years old. She attended her KG and primary school near by her home which takes her only 15 minutes on foot. She grows with her parents and two elders. She is looking happy that...her parents are both working as primary school teachers in the same school in their locality.

At present, she is attending fourth year medicine department at Hawassa University, and...Shared us her remarkable experience which lead her to join health science remembering as:

Ih...In my early grades my parents, particularly my father check through my exercise books, assist me in reading and writing skills, solving some questions...and doing my home works carefully. Gradually I started to do some of my activities independently and get interested to my subjects. Starting from the beginning of secondary school, our English teacher advised us to have study schedule, and I discussed with my father and, he arranged separate reading room to me. On program basis, sometimes I started to read and revise my subjects, and solve calculations at calm mid night, so that this became my reading habit.

Uuum...I can't remember the days I became absent or late from my class during my primary school. I prefer class participation and presentations so that it improved my confidence to deal my friends. I also used to involve in competitions like question and answer programs in my school, representing my classmates as I stood among the frontier three ranks every semester. This helped me to score high point in grade 10 and makes natural science my preferred subjects.

5.2.1. Other activities she involved during her early schooling, was asked:

During my extra time, I used to draw pictures, maps, and diagrams. Especially I like to construct parts of human body and wild animals through local materials and pieces. Sometimes, I enjoy walking and relax near big trees. As my age became mature, when I was in grade 8 I saw patients in our locality who suffered from different diseases like malaria, and I started to worry about

situations...due to lack of health services and inadequate health professionals in the locality. This brought humanitarian thinking in my life.

5.3.Mekiya's Story

The other interviewee, Mekiya Ahimed who was born in rural areas of Arsi zone is the last and the only female in her family, young and 23 years old is also attending medicine class in the same university. She said, though educated, her brothers are not successful to join higher education and are self-employed on private jobs. Further... Mekiya tried to remind us her early life experience as:

Though my brothers are not successful in their education, they advise and coach me towards my education from my early development which contributed a lot in my life. Every day, they show love to me and call me with **naked** name as 'Nurse Mekiya'

I started off thinking I wanted to go in to medicine because of my interest in science and my fascination with the way in which the human body functions. I think it runs deeper than that, when I was younger enough at grade 8, my mother suffered from a heart attack, sadly she didn't survive. I think that, this is ingrained in a part of me, I remember feeling so helpless, and the ambulance took over an hour to get to us. My mother, father, brothers and me (I was 15) went straight over to arrive at health post and obtained treatment for a moment, but she failed to follow prescriptions which could improve her problem. ---this is what I remember most specifically which I think was unconscious at that time.

I blamed myself for a long time, thinking that she might have lived if I had given her the instructions more clearly. This experience has made me want to be involved in a caring profession. I see it as an opportunity to help and prevent families who pass through similar situations.

5.3.1. Other activities she involved in her early schooling, was asked:

Woo...At my pre-school age, I enjoy playing different plays with my neighborhood children and, always I take a role of nurse and acts as a nurse. During my primary education, especially at the

beginning of grade 3, on the way to my school, I always watch health extension workers supervising our residency in small town and giving advice in aspects of environmental sanitations.

My experience and dream along with high achievements in my secondary school more derived me to give attention to science subjects, particularly Biology, and follow some medical films. During my preparatory class, I put more effort and really score high mark which helped me directly assign for medicine department.

Afterwards, I suppose for me medicine science is the knowledge and understanding I will have of the human body during and after my studies. Also, I imagine there is a massive amount of job satisfaction working as a doctor, as well as a lot of pressure that would be challenging, yet enjoyable to deal with, and successfully overcome.

5.3.2. When asked the mechanisms she accommodates reading books out of the school subject and to become clever....

Mekiya said, sometimes, I prefer to join health extension workers and talk to them. They also appraise and walk with me and share love and affection to me. Always they advise me to be strong student and have a planned study schedules for all my duties. Beside my class subjects, I prefer worships and, read spiritual books with emphasis christen Bible.

Even though the department makes my life very busy due to various burdens, and long study years with related to other departments, I am happy at my stay for this three years of study. I found the content and stuff interested me ,and at the same time I like the active and practical job ,creative, challenging and I like working under pressure and applying what I know and scenarios where I have to tackle the problem. The job satisfaction is the bonus, but I believe even if tomorrow, medicine became an average degree, I would still do it for my further study and nothing is more satisfactory than helping people.

I imagine—doctors can experience pressure while dealing with patients that often cause them depressing and stressful. For me ...why this happen is...‘because, one year you could be

transplanting organs and the next you could be growing them from stem cells. ...again one year you could be watching a disease force a death sentence and the next it could be cured. It is a challenging career with options from clinical work to research to teaching and you get to meet new interesting people every day because as a doctor you are the frontier to protecting and improving a person's quality of life.

For the purpose of our analysis, it is better to narrate on turn by turn bases of three participants. The recurrent themes of the narrative have built on the following themes; underlying reasons of choice or factors such as societal values, models, prestigious, character in a book and others; the second, decisions to study medicine in HEI and its contribution to prior school performance and the third, related to challenges of medical school students in the HEIs.

6. Factors for Choice

6.1.Gemechu

When asked **why he has chosen to study medicine**, Gemechu told us that he was surprisingly influenced by the character in the fiction his read.

The reason that caused me to join medicine was a book I read at grade seven. The book named as 'ENBUT TSIKIREDA' has influenced me to join medicine. In the book, there is a growing girl, her mother with serious illness, she is beautiful, and I hope it is around 16 year's old girl, she went to examine... the physician..... Their families have not any money to examine her mother, with this problem; the physician at that time requires some affair and asks her dating relationship.

I decided once he died is died... I wasn't prone to know the detail, why he dies? And how he dies and specific to him, I didn't have any interest

The Physician said her, if you say no, I didn't examine your mother and he said the chance of your mother is at your hand. I remember... at that time my mind decided, I learn and I should become a doctor. After I become a Physician and I decide to avoid those physicians with such undesirable behavior in the health profession.

Starting from grade seven, the only goal of my future is to become physician; no other vision is coming in my mind.

6.2.Blien

Blien also asked and responded, her life experiences to patients in early childhood as:

I see primary education age as critical time during which I developed interest towards health activities as a result of experiences I faced from people who suffered from different diseases like malaria as a result of lack of sufficient and qualified health professionals in my locality. This childhood experience has influenced my study habits and motivated me to give priority to science matter subjects.

In addition to this, the personality that I possess to be sociable and loveable to patients affected my tendency to study health matters and make me to further support people who suffered.

6.3.Mekiya's Factor for Choice

Mekiya also asked and raised her reason as:

My interest in science subjects and fascination with human body functions that I attained in science subjects played a great contribution in my aspiration to be a doctor. Moreover, the death of my mother due to heart attack led me to involve in a caring profession which could help me prevent families with a similar health problem.

On the other side, the love I had for science subjects and high scores I obtained in my secondary education further deepened my interest to study medicine department and made it the first decision during my entrance to HEI.

Furthermore, Gemechu tells us that his memorization of his elder sister in place of the character was the major factor to his decision to study medicine which signifies the influence of others.

At that time I feel just it happens to my elder sister and my mind repeatedly told me, assume that she is your sister and it made me too deeply feel my sister's pain. Still now the whole picture in my internal mind is that scenario and I only want to become physician. There is no any reason and bringing other reasons or listing has not required choosing medicine. My internal was accepted as sufficient reason.

7. Reasons of Choice

Asked Gemechu, to remember activities you might involve in you previous grades that might be related with medicine or not and he told us;

In schools I was participating on different clubs, one of them was the school's Red Cross club that I participated and later I become the coordinator from those related with health. The other, helping people was from other things I share from my mother and I also get from my readings. Together with all things in my internal the stand has created, helping people is how much satisfying is developed in my mind through time when I join the medical school.

Bilen also asked what influenced her and responded as:

Since I grow in rural community who are in shortage of infrastructures, particularly poor health services I saw the work of few doctors and health care professionals who were more or less tried to save the lives of some of the most important people in my life. Therefore, I couldn't think of a more valuable meaningful career for me.

Besides, the support and encouragement of my father who initiated me to study hard and score high grade every semester helped me to put good effort and increasingly develop my confidence to join health science and study medicine.

That_ _ _ or the fact I used to be a clever student and some of my teachers appreciation shaped me the way I keep and the ever increasing knowledge about how to balance the learning systems for good opportunities. With the same vein, the fact that I scored high point in grade 10 Ethiopian General Secondary Education Leaving Examination motivated me to join natural science class and put emphasis to chemistry and biology subjects which believed to equip students with the medicine concepts.

The other reasons that interested me are, a true sense of being able to make a difference to the community, fascination about human body, how it works, why it doesn't work, how it works, the opportunity to teach and pass my skills on to others, but mostly, more than any other profession a true sense of being able to make a difference to the community.

Surprisingly, I scored high grade in my entrance exam, and made medicine my first priority. Fortunately, I got my choice and gladly started my study. During, my stay in this university, I referred a lot of medical materials and increasingly I found it compatible to my future life.

Again---not only would it be satisfactory but if you love medicine, not only do you get to help people and make a difference but you get to work with the patients you enjoy in an analytical way, which I personally think is rewarding. I also think it is good because you take an active role in making a difference to someone's life.

Additionally, I am happy to be a doctor in medicine as it has many specialties that can make my life successful and as a health professional want to participate in research activities which could help to invent new drugs. --- Because as a career I think it would be constantly changing due to new discoveries and treatments as well as interesting and diverse. Hence, the idea of being able to use your medical knowledge to save a life, lifelong learning, job security and stability are more interesting to me.

It is my great pleasure ---if all medical professionals are honest and responsible for their job in reducing the gaps regarding health service coverage which is prevalent in our community. Surely, I believe I will become exemplar with this regard and apply my skill and knowledge with good commitment.

Mekiya on the other hand said:

I started off thinking I wanted to go in to medicine because of my interest in science and my fascination with the way in which the human body functions. I think it runs deeper than that, when I was younger enough at grade 8, my mother suffered from a heart attack, sadly she didn't survive. I think that, this is ingrained in a part of me, I remember feeling so helpless, and the ambulance took over an hour to get to us. My mother, father, brothers and me (I was 15) went straight over to arrive at health post and obtained treatment for a moment, but she failed to follow prescriptions which could improve her problem. ---this is what I remember most specifically which I think was unconscious at that time.

I blamed myself for a long time, thinking that she might have lived if I had given her the instructions more clearly.

This experience has made me want to be involved in a caring profession. I see it as an opportunity to help prevent families going through a similar situation.

My experience and dream along with high achievements in my secondary school more derived me to give attention to science subjects, particularly Biology, and follow some medical films. During my preparatory class, I put more effort and really score high mark which helped me directly assign for medicine department.

Even though the department makes my life very busy due to various burdens, and long study years with related to other departments, I am happy at my stay for this three years of study. I found the content and stuff interested me ,and at the same time I like the active and practical job ,creative, challenging and I like working under pressure and applying what I know and scenarios where I have to tackle the problem. The job satisfaction is the bonus, but I believe even if tomorrow, medicine became an average degree, I would still do it for my further study and nothing is more satisfactory than helping people.

I imagine—doctors can experience pressure while dealing with patients that often cause them depressing and stressful. For me _...why this happen is...‘ because, one year you could be transplanting organs and the next you could be growing them from stem cells. ...again one year you could be watching a disease force a death sentence and the next it could be cured. It is a challenging career with options from clinical work to research to teaching. And you get to meet new interesting people every day. As a doctor you are the frontier to protecting and improving a person’s quality of life believed to be the major reason.

The role of role model is asked and, Gemechu confirmed no one in the school joins medicine beforehand that could be model to him as:

When I was a grade 8 student, there is one individual who joined Black Lion Hospital Medical School. I was attracted by him, when he came to summer vacation. After, I start to dream that field beforehand by the aforementioned reason and I discuss with him about medicine, he also advise me also now you just arrive 9th and 10th grade, he told me to pay attention to biology and other relates and also he brings materials beyond my stage and I also read

When I am also in high school, he helps me to understand the medical word, the medical education

Bilen also has no model to refer but she said:

The appreciation I obtained from my father and an encouragement provided by some of my teachers is undeniable contributors for my achievement.

On the other hand, Mekiya took the initiatives that her brothers call her with her ‘naked name’ which gradually influenced her preference to health professionals, being playing as a nurse. Again, the presences of health extension worker that create too closely talk and enjoy with her greatly influenced her interest towards health professions. This improved her life and really helped her to be a doctor.

8. Challenges in Medical School

Some of the challenges raised in medicine school are also summarized as:

Bilen and Mekiya raised similar experiences with regard to their stay in studying medicine in the university. To mention few, they raised that every discipline demands hardworking and intensive study. Health science, medicine in particular requires wider study hours and long years of study. The nature of courses is broad to cover and tired some to understand its theoretical and practical skills and knowledge.

The fact that the subjects need more supplementary reading materials which incurs financial supports is one of the challenges, especially for those students that have limited financial and moral supports.

They explained their personal observation that, there are some classmates who are disqualified from their study and are also some students who go in to different addictive behaviors which surprisingly distort their study. The problem is getting sever since the placement is only score based and aptitude tests are not used.

9. Other Medical Students Reasons of Choice

R: Reasons of your classmates in medical school or in prior schools

In our dorms we talk each other, some hesitates “zimibeye new shimideda yegebahut” (I join unconsciously to study field of Rote memorization), and questions rose on the why of joining medicine?

At that time my reason was unique, but most of my classmates reasoned out the values the society give for medical discipline is the major reason. The prestigious values in the society emanated from the service the medical related with the name of the profession as related with the societal value

When you are clever, you perceived to hold the highest post, those students who perform high, allowed and selected to join medicine. They were clever students, to get medicine is one of the reasons the society valued

In terms of income, medical doctors get a lot of money (“hakim bizu yagegnal”) and they raised reasons as becoming rich

Most of them, reason out in two of the reason, money and societal prestige value. In addition to the aforementioned Gemechu’s reason, the other two likely *reasons of him to choice medicine are, the influence of her sister and mother and his engagement in the Red Cross club in high school beyond his reading. The narrative identifies, he has motives like helping people and bringing profound change in the unethical practices observed in the health service.*

Additionally, we asked Gemechu to describe his performance in schools, the way he learn and subjects he perform and relationship with teachers; he told us With relation to school activities Gemechu mentioned: Like other students, I haven’t supported by books, and other additional materials; When a teacher teaches, I didn’t miss it, I finish what he taught there, I understood and exit the class, I ask there for concepts that I didn’t understood, afterward no need of reading

My experience in subjects and participation, for instance physics, chemistry, mathematics related things my activities were believed to be very good. However, I am good in other subjects as compared to biology performance. Specifically, we assume biology is related with medicine, throughout my school life the biology performance is not better than physics, mathematics and chemistry. My mind sets a goal only to become a medical Doctor and I didn't think twice, when choice was come after I took a grade 10 exam, I am the top scorer from the school and all over the zone and we allowed to select social and Natural. I did not have anything to think, I thought only things that took me to my dream of pursuing medical study.

I remember, my history teacher, now holding his PhD from —sedist Killo University and currently he is in the teaching career. When I was choosing natural science, my history teacher disputed with me because he appreciated my performance in history. Soon, we joined grade 11th and in grade 11th and 12th and latter I sat to leaving exam and I didn't dream any field other than medicine. I select medicine as my first choice and I got my physics teacher, he become disgusted like the history teacher on my choice. This all stable aspiration to medicine field is because of the influence of the character I read during grade seven.

To be a medicine student, I know what is expected from me and to score high is the only option that I have.

Regarding Challenges that Blocks his goals in School, Gemechu stated as: I was preparing for the final exam scoring high has expected to enter medical school, unless and other wise my dream is not realized. I am in the school, for the last four years no one was score high and join the medical school. However, my first semester grade 12th rank was fourth that caused me to frustrate and my mind asked me, if you can't compute with your classmates, how your goal will be fulfilled. It made me not to study, instead I play football and one day my civic teacher asks me about the situation and later he advises me to read. Further, he looks after my activities, fulfilling materials and other moral support. Through his close inspection I start hardly studying, due to his support my score is the highest not only from the school but also to the zone.

10. Conclusions

The right major choice for the students entering in to the professional education is critical having high impact on their professional life and future achievements. This is the turning point; it cannot be left, on intuition, preconceive notions, wild imaginations or popular concepts. A miss-perceived career choice directs all individual efforts and resources in to wrong direction, when not aligned with the expectations; would not only be frustrating rather draining of the individual energy and wastage of resources. The re-alignment is possible, but it has serious implications in terms of time, money and motivation. The career choice of the students must need to be based on; strong knowledge, complete information, and appropriately guided, matching individual personality type and other intrinsic and extrinsic factors.

This study is aimed at an investigation of the Hawassa University College of Health Sciences students' career choice for medicine by examining their aspirations, role models, interests towards medicine, and career decision status. The sample of three fourth year students were selected purposely for the study and deep interview was conducted. It was concluded that, a relatively a strong sense of major choice, and greater career decidedness exist among these students. This was emerged from their overall story reports.

Assisting students with life transitions through the provision of life experiences at schools, colleges and universities is the role of diversified bodies: families, guardians, peers, teachers, professionals and the others.

11. Implications

The students need to be oriented on new emerging trends, future opportunities and challenges in the context of career choice options. They need to know the prevalent market trends and practices and job scenario of various sectors. To achieve this purpose, it is expected that educators help students identify career objectives and secure employment by encouraging students to explore their values and interests.

The vocational guidance practices at Hawassa University are consequent in line with current understandings that students should be provided with an opportunity to unearth career possibilities discover leading edge interests, assess problems, motivate constructive behavior as

well as acquire a cognitive structure for evaluating career alternatives, clarifying expectations, planning interventions and establishing ability range.

Even though it is difficult to generalize from only three sample students, other strand of results reveal that gender has no effect on levels of vocational and career decision status among university students. But, the interviewee result confirmed that, the academic standing has an effect on career decision in career satisfaction in particular.

Based on the above discussion, it can be said that, the students at Hawassa University are provided with high levels of vocational guidance. This helps them to have a clear and stable picture of their goals, interest, personality and talents that lead, in turn, to relatively untroubled decision making and confidence in one's ability to make good decisions regarding major and future careers.

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